

DESIGNING PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL SPACE

Azamova Barno

Teacher of Namangan State University

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Annotation: At present, information technology has become an integral element of the educational process, providing a new look at the modern education system. In this context, educational activity forms an open pedagogical system, with the main focus on the development of intellectual, creative and culturally developed personalities. The article clarifies the essence and purpose of the digital educational environment to improve the quality of education and the harmonious development of the individual.

Keywords: digital educational environment, interaction, distance learning, personality, information technology, competence, design, activity, psychological and pedagogical tools.

Introduction: Definition of the problem in general terms and its relationship to key scientific and practical issues. Currently, Russian society is going through global transformations in the political, social, economic and cultural fields. Such changes require an adequate development of the higher education system, which includes innovative approaches in theoretical and practical didactics. As a result of the emerging needs, the modern educational environment is beginning to integrate digital technologies, which stimulates the search for new methods and forms of organizing the educational process. In the last century, attempts have already been made to include information media in the educational process, but at that time digital technologies were not sufficiently developed, and neither teachers nor students were ready to use computers as everyday educational tools. In our time, information technology has become an integral part of the educational process, as it allows you to look at the modern education system from a new perspective. The digital educational environment consists of interrelated components: computer learning tools, communication tools, innovative pedagogical technologies and information resources. In this context, educational activity is an open pedagogical system, the main goal of which is the formation of an intellectually, creatively and culturally developed personality[13].

Analysis of recent studies and publications covering aspects of this problem and on which the author is based; identifying previously unresolved parts of a common problem. The problem of developing a digital educational environment in the modern education system is the subject of attention of every educational institution, since the requirements of the federal state educational standards of higher education are aimed at creating an information space for students.

There are many different approaches to digital education.

environment. Goryunova M.A. argues that in the implementation of the digital educational environment, priority is given to pedagogical goals. Krasilnikova V.A. notes that the information space is necessary to enhance cognitive activity students, since this ensures

the functioning of psychological conditions, innovative pedagogical technologies and software and methodological teaching aids [2].

According to Abrosimov A.G. The digital educational environment is a system that combines information potential, software, hardware and telecommunications resources. Melnikova E.V. reveals the digital environment as a set of software and hardware components and psychological and pedagogical tools for information interaction of all participants in the pedagogical process. Thus, the digital educational environment is understood as a single information space that provides organizational support for the entire pedagogical process, scientific research, professional development of teachers and students. *The relevance of the study is substantiated.* Designing a digital educational environment in modern conditions will allow information technologies to be the basis for ensuring the effectiveness and development of the pedagogical process, the interaction of all subjects of the educational process. In the formation of a digital educational environment, a comprehensively trained graduate is being prepared, possessing the necessary competencies, capable of life in a highly developed information society.

Methodology: Determining the purpose of the article. The main purpose of this article is to explore the impact of the digital educational environment on the quality of training of highly qualified specialists, the effectiveness of the educational process and the cooperation of all participants in the learning process. **Task formulation.** In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks must be completed:

- deepen understanding of the essence and purpose of the digital educational environment in order to improve the quality of education and the harmonious development of individuality;
- to study the main components that are required for the development of a digital educational environment in an educational institution of higher education;
- explore the opportunities for implementing a digital educational environment and the tools needed to create it.

Applied methods, approaches and technologies. This article examines the key aspects of the effective operation of the digital educational environment in the modern educational context, as well as systematization and deductive analysis of the information received.

RESULTS

Presentation of the main material of the study with a full justification of the obtained scientific results. The concept of a digital educational environment is relatively new. The introduction of information technologies is aimed at activating computer resources, educational and scientific material, leading to the professional development of the student's personality. The digital educational environment and the favorable conditions created in it contribute to the growth of intellectual competence, the potential of teachers and students. Let's define the components necessary for designing a digital educational environment of a higher educational institution:

- 1) scientific and technical support, including computers, literary sources, scientific materials [4];
- 2) communicative support, which consists in the implementation of interaction between teachers and students;
- 3) information support, involving access to electronic media, knowledge about how to obtain, search, systematize information. When starting to design a digital educational

environment, one should also take into account the specific features of the higher education system, and in the future - innovative approaches to managing the educational process, professional training of teachers and requirements for improving information competence [5]. The digital educational environment involves a system of information and communication tools, the implementation of which is aimed at fulfilling the requirements of the federal state educational standard of higher education on the formation of conditions for the implementation of the educational program of higher education, which contributes to the achievement of high results by students in the learning process. It should be noted that the digital educational environment in the modern education system is becoming a single communication space for all participants in the pedagogical process. Let's analyze the implementation of the digital educational environment at the NSPU. K. Minina on the example of teaching the discipline "Pedagogical technologies". To design a digital educational environment, its means should be considered.

First, it is a local area network that operates on the basis of the global Internet and provides remote access to electronic devices. Its implementation takes place on the basis of telecommunication networks, due to which the integration of a computer system for information exchange is realized [6]. Thanks to this tool of the digital educational environment, the teacher is able to assist students with homework, can ask additional questions without being present next to the students.

secondly, it is a computer, which is a didactic tool for increasing the efficiency of the pedagogical process in an educational institution. The presence of computers in the teaching of the discipline "Pedagogical technologies" ensures the preparation of each student on the topic chosen by him. For example, one student is preparing a presentation on the technology of discussion learning, the other is considering technologies, the third is design technologies. At the same time, by combining computers in the classroom into one system, the teacher can check the presence and result of the completed task without leaving his place.

Thirdly, these are public information tools that provide storage of a single database of a higher educational institution. To such resources should include projectors, web-cameras, multimedia equipment, interactive devices, scanners and printers. Such tools provide a visual representation of the prepared material when studying Research Institute of the discipline "Pedagogical Technologies". Let's consider the possibilities for implementing a digital educational environment in a higher educational institution:

- search and transfer of educational material, both in text, and graphic and sound format, the ability to quickly provide information on the work done;
- storage and processing of information, which also involves the systematization of materials in electronic databases [7];
- the possibility of conducting audio and video conferences, exchanging information with a large number of participants, organizing information communities. The digital educational environment implies continuous cooperation between teachers and students, a characteristic feature of which is the nature of interaction. In an innovative educational environment the teacher takes the place of the mentor of the educational process, which develops the cognitive and creative activity of students [8]. As another possibility for the formation of a digital educational environment is the implementation of distance learning, which has become widespread, since it meets the requirements of information technology [9]. The purpose of distance learning is to provide students with the elements of universal

education, which are aimed at the possibility of effective development of the individual. The teacher takes a responsible place for students to achieve the planned learning outcomes. The most important feature of distance learning is the preservation of interaction between the subjects of the educational process. Forms of distance learning include video lectures, video conferences, training sessions, webinar [10-13]. This form of education is aimed at the comprehensive development of the student's personality, effective planning of time for training sessions, active use of self-development opportunities, the formation of responsibility, organization. The digital educational environment with the help of the considered components and methods is a platform for a holistic creative process of education. Information technologies provide wide interaction in the course of implementation of joint creative projects. Students take an active part in the implementation of the educational process, which contributes to improving the quality and efficiency of education.

Comparison of the received results with results in other researches. The article clarified the essence and purpose of the digital educational environment for the professional development of the personality of students and teachers. An analysis of the components and methods for designing a digital educational environment has determined the main guidelines for improving the quality of education.

CONCLUSIONS

Research findings. The digital educational environment of a higher educational institution is a dynamically developing system for the effective implementation of information and communication services. In the process of designing a digital educational environment when studying the discipline "Pedagogical technologies" there is an increase in the efficiency and quality of the learning process through the introduction of computer resources, ensuring interaction. The implementation of the digital educational environment ensures the formation of a comprehensively prepared person with the necessary competencies, capable of successful activity in a highly developed information society.

Prospects for further research in this direction. It is necessary to study the features of the influence of the digital educational environment on the opportunities for self-education of teachers and students. The involvement of teachers and students in the design of the educational environment entails the development of a closer connection between traditional and innovative pedagogical technologies.

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